

Fitting of data: JBW-NP-P-5NM-V1 2021-02-18_10-06-19
 $0.0201 \leq q \text{ (nm}^{-1}\text{)} \leq 24$
Active parameters: 1, ranges: 1
Background level: 0.00804 ± 0.000845
(Scaling factor: $1.06\text{e}+34 \pm 3.5\text{e}+31$)
Timing: 10 repetitions of 49.9 ± 7.94 seconds

Range $1.500\text{e}-10$ to $1.500\text{e}-07$, vol-weighted
totalValue: $1.192\text{e}-03 \pm 3.123\text{e}-06$
mean: $5.262\text{e}-09 \pm 3.457\text{e}-12$
variance: $1.761\text{e}-18 \pm 2.757\text{e}-20$
skew: $2.696\text{e}-01 \pm 4.402\text{e}-02$
kurtosis: $2.949\text{e}+00 \pm 1.231\text{e}-01$

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